

Decentralized image upload and sharing using Blockchain

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Abstract— The rise of digital information and the need for safe, unchangeable data storage in recent years gave rise to decentralized technology. Blockchain, which is a form of distributed ledger technology, offers a new way to develop decentralized applications that are more secure and reliable. In this regard, the research focuses on the development of a decentralized platform for image upload and sharing using blockchain technology precisely Ethereum smart contracts, IPFS for decentralized storage and React for the front-end user interface.

Keywords—Blockchain, IPFS, Solidity, Smart Contracts, Data Security, Ethereum

1. INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution changed the way we consume and disseminate information, resulting in a quantum growth of data creation and distribution. On the contrary, the advent of the digital era also implies confrontations with security and privacy. Centralized platforms have been leading the digital environment for decades, and they have been largely criticized for problems with data leakages and centralized control over users' data. Decentralized technologies, such as bitcoin and IPFS (Inter Planetary File System), have garnered popularity as solutions to these problems because of their ability to handle concerns about data security, privacy, and sovereignty. Blockchain, which is renowned for its distributed structure and immutability, offers a revolutionary approach to the management, storage, and access of data. By offering a decentralized storage system that guarantees data availability and integrity, IPFS enhances blockchain technology. This study investigates the combination of IPFS and blockchain technology for decentralized image uploading and sharing. With a foundation in decentralization, data ownership, and access control, the project seeks to provide users with a safe and independent platform for exchanging images. By leveraging Solidity for smart contract development on the Ethereum blockchain and React for the front-end interface, this project demonstrates the practical implementation of a decentralized image sharing ecosystem. Key features include decentralized storage on IPFS, smart contract-based access control, and user-centric ownership management. These features collectively contribute to a seamless and secure image sharing experience, where users retain control over their data and access permissions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Singh, et al.[1] describes a blockchain-based system intended for safe exchange of medical data. To solve issues with safe

record sharing, it integrates a distributed authentication system and tamper-proof identity management. The paper highlights the benefits of blockchain technology in boosting security and privacy in medical record management systems and assesses the solution's efficacy using BAN logic.

A decentralized IPFS and blockchain-based application for distributed file storage in vehicle networks is suggested in the paper by Sangeeta and Nam [2]. The technology allows different file formats to be uploaded to a decentralized application (DApp), and it ensures immutability by storing file hashes on the Ethereum blockchain through smart contracts. Furthermore, the DApp has a keyword search function made possible by contract .queryFilter and Ethers.js' smart contract event listener, which improves data accessibility and transparency while preserving system resilience.

Singla et al. [3] proposed a smart contract architecture for a Leave Management System using Solidity and Ethereum, integrating smartphones as IoT devices and an alternative centralized architecture with a Blockchain backend to address resource constraints.

V, et al. [4] explores a framework for safe academic research record keeping is presented that combines blockchain, IPFS, and conventional encryption techniques. The method makes use of Ethereum smart contracts to store IPFS metadata on the blockchain, guaranteeing the production of unchangeable records appropriate for auditing. This framework tackles issues with access control, record tampering, and information leakage in research data management.

Anthal, et al. [5] explores the challenges of centralized file sharing servers, such as security and privacy issues. It then discusses how blockchain and IPFS offer decentralized and secure alternatives, examining projects like File Coin that use these technologies for renting storage space. The paper also compares IPFS with other decentralized storage solutions and evaluates the potential impact of blockchain and IPFS on sectors like media, entertainment, and healthcare, highlighting their promise for secure and efficient file sharing.

In the article by Jadhav et al. [6], they discuss blockchain-based decentralized file sharing and its potential to transform data sharing processes, addressing scalability and privacy issues. The paper discusses blockchain-based decentralized file sharing and its potential benefits, including improved security and openness. It addresses scalability and privacy issues while showcasing active decentralized file sharing

networks. Overall, it suggests that this technology could revolutionize how we share and store files.

In the article by Kang et al. [7], the authors present a blockchain-based private file storage and sharing method incorporating Interplanetary File System (IPFS) and Named Data Network (NDN). This method employs NDN for file content signature and encryption, separates file security and transmission processes, utilizes a flexible NDN reverse path forwarding and routing strategy, integrates an IPFS private storage network for enhanced security, and ensures traceability through consensus among participating nodes in a synchronized blockchain.

In the literature review by Athanere and Thakur [8], they propose a blockchain-based secure decentralized system using IPFS for secure data transfer. This system employs two-level key management: the data owner encrypts the file, and the IPFS server generates a hash code of the encrypted file. This approach offers several advantages, including handling consumers across multiple domains, reducing single-point failure risks, decreasing communication and computation overhead at the consumer level, and effectively resisting malicious attacks from both single and collaborative sources.

3. METHODOLOGY

The demand for secure decentralized solutions for file storage and sharing is becoming essential in the modern digital age. Traditional centralized platforms and services are plagued with security issues and ownership difficulties, making them vulnerable to being replaced by decentralized technologies, such as blockchain and IPFS. This paper discusses the unique creation of a decentralized image upload and sharing platform; the focus is on utilizing Solidity, a blockchain programming language, as well as React, an intuitive front-end interface. This project's major goal is to give users a reliable, safe, and unchangeable way to publish and share images while keeping complete control over who may view them and who owns them. Users may regulate access authorization precisely, grant or refuse access to specific individuals, and have complete control over the content they contribute by utilizing Solidity smart contracts on a blockchain network such as Ethereum. In addition, the incorporation of IPFS for decentralized storage guarantees data availability and integrity throughout the network, augmenting the dependability and robustness of the platform.

The advanced decentralized image uploading and sharing platform offers the following notable components:

1. Decentralized Storage: Decentralized capability and IPFS support secure and tamper-resistant image storage, boosting security and ensuring data integrity.
2. Smart Contract Mechanism: The use of Solidity smart contracts assists in implementing robust access control and ownership management for images uploaded, allowing users to exercise fine-grained control over their shared files.
3. Access Control: Users can choose who has access to their images and how long access rights endure, ensuring a secure and personalized image-sharing experience that places a premium on privacy and data ownership.

This research paper thoroughly explores the technical intricacies of implementing these features using Solidity for smart contract development and React for the user-friendly

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front-end interface. The fusion of blockchain technology, decentralized storage, and robust access control mechanisms forms the backbone of this platform, offering a comprehensive solution for secure, efficient, and user-controlled image sharing within a decentralized ecosystem.

3.1 Blockchain

Blockchain is a decentralized, distributed technology of digital ledger, recording the transaction in multiple computers safely and transparently without any alteration. "Block" a Transaction is added to a chain of "Block" linked to cryptographically, a block stores information, and a chain of blocks is called a blockchain. Each "block" has a timestamp, transaction data, hash of its own and hash of previous block, which makes difficult to alter the data. It is a decentralized system overall. The new block appending that to the blockchain is the only and the only true version that is agreed by all nodes in the Blockchain. It refers to the collective maintenance of a technical solution that maintains a continuous record file as a reliable database through decentralization.

3.2 Working of Blockchain

As illustrated in Figure 1 when a new transaction occurs, the from a peer-to-peer computer to a network of decentralized computers globally. These computers, referred to as miners, confirm the transaction's legitimacy by solving equations. Once done, the transactions are compiled into blocks. Miners are compensated for their efforts, as can be seen from block one to the last block. All these blocks are connected in a sequence and become an immutable record of all transactions; hence a permanent transaction history.

Figure 1 :Working of Blockchain

3.3 Blockchain Features

1. Decentralization: Unlike traditional centralized systems where a single authority controls the data, blockchain operates on a decentralized network of nodes (computers) that collectively maintain and validate the data.
2. Transparency: Transactions on the blockchain are transparent and accessible to all participants in the network. This transparency promotes trust and reduces the potential for fraud.
3. Immutability: Once a transaction is recorded on the blockchain, it cannot be altered or deleted. This immutability ensures the integrity of the data and prevents unauthorized changes.

4. Security. Blockchain employs cryptographic methods to secure transactions and data, rendering it practically impossible for hacking and tempering. It is nearly impossible to hack the blockchain or modify the data that has already been recorded .

5. Smart contracts. Self-executing contracts with predetermined rules and conditions expressed in code are used in smart contracts . They run by themselves and automatically address deals based on their criteria without any intermediaries.

3.4 System Model

The Ethereum Network will be used as the primary blockchain for the implementation of the proposed system, which is a decentralized application (Dapp) that will handle all transactional data and record-keeping pertaining to the products of the enterprises listed on Dapp. Figure 2 displays the fundamental design of the system.

Figure 2 : System Architecture

3.4.1 Ethereum

The decentralized blockchain uses a consensus method based on proof-of-work. Blocks are added to the blockchain by proof-of-work, which requires solving mathematical puzzles. Nodes verify that they have committed computing resources to the task by solving these puzzles, which validates the addition of a block to the blockchain. In Ethereum (ETH), this validation procedure known as mining pays off when a new block is successfully added. Although mining frequently entails a great deal of trial and error, when it is done well, blocks are added to and recorded in the blockchain.

3.4.2 Smart Contract

Smart contracts are programs that are stored inside Blocks. Through them, transactions no longer require middlemen. When certain criteria are met, these contracts function as protocols and take automatic action. Smart contracts have the important feature of being unchangeable once they are implemented, which protects them from outside interference or modification.

3.4.3 IPFS

Storing large files directly on blockchains can lead to inefficiencies. The blockchain network becomes burdened with excessive data that must be shared among nodes, consuming storage space and increasing operational costs. IPFS offers a solution by efficiently storing and sharing large files through cryptographic hashes, which can be recorded on a blockchain. However, IPFS lacks the ability to selectively share files, posing challenges for sharing sensitive data. To

address this limitation, this paper introduces a modified IPFS version that integrates with Ethereum smart contracts for access-controlled file sharing. A smart contract manages the access control list, while the modified IPFS software enforces these access rules. This setup allows for secure and controlled sharing of files, with interactions between the IPFS system and smart contract ensuring proper enforcement of access permissions. The paper evaluates the impact of this access-controlled IPFS setup through experimental analysis and discussion.

3.5 Implementation

Building a blockchain-based decentralized image upload and sharing model requires several important steps:

1. Requirements Gathering

First, analyse the workflows and identify main points. Determine the functional and non-functional requirements including security, privacy, scalability needs.

2. Blockchain Platform Selection

Evaluate different blockchain protocols and architectures like Ethereum, Hyperledger Fabric based on the requirements and access control needs. Prototype on testnets to assess platforms. Consider development costs, transaction fees and scalability.

```
PS C:\Users\jaimo\OneDrive\Desktop\Drive3.0-main> npx hardhat node
Started HTTP and WebSocket JSON-RPC server at http://127.0.0.1:8545/

Accounts
=====
WARNING: These accounts, and their private keys, are publicly known.
Any funds sent to them on Mainnet or any other live network WILL BE LOST.

Account #0: 0xf39fd65e1aad88f6f4ce6a882727cffff92266 (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0xac0974bec39a17e36ba4b64d238ff944abcf48cbcd5efcaee784d7b4f2ff80

Account #1: 0x70997978c51812dc3a010c7d01b50e0d17dc79c8 (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x59c6995e998f97a5a0044966f0945389dc9e86dae88c7a8421f4603b6b78690d

Account #2: 0x3c44cd8db6a900fa2b585dd299e03d12FA4293BC (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x5de4111fa1a4b94988f83103eb1f706367c2e68ca870fc3fb9a804cdab365a

Account #3: 0x90f79bfe62c4f870365e785b2211f101E93b906 (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x7c852118294e51653712a81e05800f419141751be58f605c371e15141b007a6

Account #4: 0x15d34AAf54267087Dc367839AAf71A00a2C6A65 (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x47e179ec197488593b187f80a00eb0da91f1b9d0b13f8733639f19c30a34926a

Account #5: 0x9965907d1a55bc2695c58ba16fB37d81980A4dc (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x8b3a350cf5c34c9194ca85829a2df0ec3153be03185e2d33488872092edfba

Account #6: 0x976EA74026E726554db657fA547b3adBc3a0a9 (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x92db14e403b83df3e3f233f83dFa390d7096F21ca9b0dd6d888b2b4ec1564e

Account #7: 0x14dC79964da2C88b23698B3D3cc7Ca23193d9955 (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x4bbbf85ce3377467afe5d46f804f22181302bb7f24d81f601fcd9b7cfb4356

Account #8: 0x23618e1E3f5cdf7F54C3d65f7Bc0aBf521E8F (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0xdba1821B80551c965939329250298a3472ba22fee921c0cf5d620ea67b97

Account #9: 0xa0Ee7A142d267C1f36714E4a8F76212F20a79720 (10000 ETH)
Private Key: 0x2a871d078b97d79848a013d4096a73bf4cc922c82533c1cf7073df6d4d09c6
```

3. Develop Smart Contracts in Solidity

Write Solidity smart contracts to manage image ownership and access control. Include functions for uploading images, granting/rejecting access, and managing ownership.

```
DEPLOY & RUN TRANSACTIONS
// SPDX-License-Identifier: GPL-3.0
pragma solidity >=0.7.0 <=0.9.0;

contract Upload {
    struct Access {
        address user;
        bool access;
    }
    mapping(address=>string[]) url; //to store the url
    mapping(address=>mapping(address=>bool)) ownership;
    mapping(address=>Access[]) accessList; //to give ownership
    mapping(address=>mapping(address=>bool)) previousData;

    function add(address _user, string calldata url) external {
        url[_user].push(url);
    }

    function allow(address user) external {
        ownership[user].push(url);
        if(previousData[user].sender != true) {
            for(uint i; i < accessList[user].length; i++) {
                if(accessList[user].sender[i].user == user) {
                    accessList[user].access[i] = true;
                }
            }
        }
    }
}
```

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4. Build React Front-End Interface:

Create a React application for the front-end interface. Include features for user authentication, image upload, access control management, and image display.

5. Integrate IPFS for Decentralized Storage

Set up an IPFS node or use a public IPFS gateway for storage. Implement IPFS upload functionality in your React front-end to securely upload images to IPFS.

Figure 3 : Landing Page

6. Connect Front-End with Blockchain:

Use web3.js or ethers.js to connect your React front-end to the Ethereum blockchain. Implement functions to interact with smart contracts, such as uploading images, managing access, and querying ownership.

7. Smart contract Deployment:

Deploy your smart contracts to the Ethereum blockchain and deploy your React front-end to a hosting service.

hardhat: This is the core package of Hardhat, a development environment and build tool for Ethereum smart contract development. It allows you to write, compile, test, and deploy smart contracts on the Ethereum blockchain.

The command 'npx hardhat run scripts/deploy.js --network localhost' is used to deploy a smart contract using Hardhat on a local Ethereum network (localhost).

```
PS C:\Users\jaimo\OneDrive\Desktop\Dgdrive3.0-main> npx hardhat run scripts/deploy.js --network localhost
Library deployed to: 0x5FbDB2315678afecb367f032d93F642f64180aa3
```

8. Result and Discussion

The result of the project is a decentralized image upload and sharing platform that employs blockchain technology, namely Ethereum and Solidity, alongside decentralized storage through IPFS. This platform allows users to securely upload images, which are then stored in a decentralized and immutable manner on IPFS. Smart contracts written in Solidity on the Ethereum blockchain manage access control and ownership, enabling users to grant or revoke access to their uploaded images to specific individuals.

Figure 4 : Connecting to Ethereum using MetaMask wallet

A MetaMask confirmation popup is displayed which asks for the confirmation as in Figure .

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Figure 5 :Completing the transaction with MetaMask wallet

After confirming, the block containing all details is added to the blockchain, and a success page similar to Figure 7 is displayed.

Figure 7 : Message after addition of block to blockchain

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the decentralized image upload and sharing platform developed using blockchain technology, Solidity smart contracts, React front-end interface, and IPFS for storage offers a secure and user-controlled environment for sharing images. By leveraging the decentralized nature of blockchain and IPFS, the platform ensures data integrity, privacy, and resilience against centralized failures. The implementation of access control and ownership management through smart contracts empowers users to dictate who can access their uploaded images, enhancing privacy and security. Overall, this project demonstrates the potential of decentralized technologies in creating robust and user-centric applications for data sharing and management.

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